

Studies on the effects of cyclohexylbenzthiazylsulfenamide accelerated sulfur vulcanization of natural rubber. Part-I. Kinetics of vulcanization

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Cyclohexylbenzthiazylsulfenamide (CBS) is used as delayed action accelerator for the sulfur vulcanization of elastomers. It is now finding increasing application with ultra accelerators like tetramethyl thiuram disulfide (TMTD) and zinc diethyl dithiocarbamate (ZDC) in the vulcanization of natural rubber (NR). The evaluation of kinetic studies on accelerator blends (CBS/TMTD and CBS/ZDC) is described. The kinetics of crosslink formation by blend systems vary markedly with formulations and the type of ultra accelerator being used. The crosslinking rate of NR gum stock in the absence of ultra accelerator is first order. However, the blend system gives crosslinking rate of dual nature. The rate shows first order at the initial part (low temperature near about 120°) and higher order at the later part of vulcanization (high temperature near about 140°). The activity of ultra accelerator fragments alters the amine moiety of sulfenamide system according to their chemical structure.

Vulcanization allows a wide latitude in compounding techniques which can lead to a great variety of molecular structures and which in turn can give unique properties. In the case of accelerated sulfur vulcanization, the composition of the curing system determines the characteristics of the vulcanization process and the structure of the vulcanizate network¹. Accelerator selection is very important. The major chemical functions of accelerators in conjunction with auxiliary agents such as zinc oxide and stearic acid are many. The induction period of the vulcanization (scorch safety) and rate of vulcanization after the induction period at a given temperature depend on accelerator/activator system. The concentrations of both accelerator and sulfur (sulfur accelerator ratio) have a profound effect on the extent of vulcanization and on the thermal stability of the vulcanizate network. Moreover, rubber vulcanizates show considerable changes in their physical properties for oxidative ageing². It depends markedly on the type and degree of cure.

The present paper describes the vulcanization kinetics of a very popular and industrially important accelerator CBS with sulfur and also its blends with TMTD and ZDC on the vulcanization of natural rubber. Scheele and Helberg³ investigated vulcanization of natural and synthetic rubbers with sulfur in presence of sulfenamides. Wheelams⁴ examined a series of sulfenamide accelerators for safety and cure rate. Some investigators have felt that the mechanism involves free radicals⁵. Ionic mechanism has also been postulated⁶. Mortia *et al.*⁷ tried to explain the order of the crosslinking

reactions. Therefore, vulcanization kinetics are still a matter of investigation particularly for blend accelerator systems. The present communication reports the results of the kinetic study on the effects of cyclohexylbenzthiazylsulfenamide accelerated sulfur vulcanization of natural rubber.

Results and discussion

Rheographs were obtained from the experimented compounds (mix formulation in Table 1). Various cure parameters and their corresponding rheometer torque presentations are shown in Fig. 1. The data at 140° are shown in Table 2. At the start of the discussion let us assume that these crosslink formation is first order after an induction period t_i , then according to Coran's model^{7a}

$$dV_u / dt = k_1 (V_{u\infty} - V_{ut}) \quad (1)$$

where V_{ut} is the crosslink density at time t , $V_{u\infty}$ the crosslink density at infinite time, k_1 the first order rate constant. On integration eqn. (1) gives

$$V_{ut} = V_{u\infty} e^{k_1 \{1 - (t-t_i)\}},$$

where t_i is the delay time.

$$\text{or, } \ln (V_{u\infty} - V_{ut}) = \ln V_{u\infty} - k_1 (t - t_i) \quad (2)$$

It is established that rheometer torque is proportional to crosslink density³. Thus eqn. (2) becomes

$$\ln (R_{\infty} - R_t) = -k_1 (t - t_i) + \ln (R_{\infty} - R_0)$$

Table 1. Basic recipe of the mixes

Mix →	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Ingredients (in parts by weight)									
↓									
Natural Rubber (RMA1)	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Zinc oxide	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
Stearic acid	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
IPPD*	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Sulfur	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
CBS	0.6	0.8	1.0	1.2	0.6	0.8	1.0	0.6	0.8
TMTD	–	–	–	–	0.4	0.4	0.4	–	–
ZDC	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.4	0.4

*IPPD (*N*-isopropyl-*N'*-phenyl-*p*-phenylenediamine).

where R_0 is the value at time t_i .

$$\ln \left\{ \frac{(R_\infty - R_t)}{(R_\infty - R_0)} \right\} = -k_1(t - t_i) \quad (3)$$

The plots of $\log (R_\infty - R_t) / (R_\infty - R_0)$ versus cure time at 140° drawn from these curves are shown in Fig. 2. The straight line plots (linearity) of the CBS mix systems (A, B, C and D) indicate first order rate of crosslinking. But the plots of the blend accelerator systems appear linear at the early part of the vulcanization and non-linear at the later part.

Fig. 1. Plot of rheometer torque vs cure time.

So vulcanization reaction rate of the blend systems are initially first order and then higher order. Scheele and Hillmer⁸ observed analogous results for NR tread stocks

cured by PTT (bis piperidino thiocarbonyl tetrasulfide) and TMTD. It is significant that all blend systems show higher cure rate than any mix containing CBS alone, and CBS/ZDC blend systems show the highest cure rate. The data in Table 2 also indicate that CBS mixes give the longest scorch delay and highest optimum cure time (t_{90}) or in other words, lowest crosslink efficiency. The highest R_∞ value is obtained by CBS/ZDC (Stock H), which shows poor scorch delay. Again among CBS/ZDC system, Stock I gives the highest cure rate and shortest scorch delay. Table 2 also shows that the activities (cure rates) of CBS/ZDC combined accelerator mixes are different to that of CBS/TMTD mixes NR stocks. The activation energies (Table 2) of the mixes support the above facts. The variation of M_c (Table 2) is also explained by the variation of activation energies of the mixes.

The quantitative study of crosslink formation during the vulcanization of NR gum stock by sulfenamide accelerator was reported to be first order rate kinetics⁸. The plots derived from the present rheometer cure curves are given in Fig. 2. The present results of NR gum stocks by CBS are in agreement with the previous studies⁸. However, in the case of CBS/TMTD or CBS/ZDC combined accelerator system it appears that the crosslinking reaction does proceed initially (temperature near about 120°) by a first order rate, but a major part by higher order rate kinetics (temperature 140° or more). Rubber is a bad conductor of heat. So temperature of the mix rises slowly to attend cure temperature. As a result temperature variation occurs with time.

The second order rate constants of the blend system mixes can be derived from the rheographs by assuming that intermediates, which are initially formed, react bimolecularly to form effective crosslinks⁹. Let us assume, ∞ is a constant.

Table 2. CBS accelerator and its mixes with TMTD and ZDC accelerators in NR stocks rheometer cure at 140°

Test mix compd.	Scorch time (t ₂) (min)	Optimum cure time (t ₉₀) (min)	R _∞	Cure rate ^a (lb/min)	K ^b	αk _x	M _c × 10 ⁻³	E (kcal/mol)
A	12.50	20.00	35.00	3.67	0.800	0.051	4.75	19.14
B	11.50	18.25	31.50	5.10	0.950	0.070	2.70	17.37
C	11.36	15.00	30.50	8.36	1.760	0.135	2.41	11.71
D	10.75	12.50	37.50	12.00	2.570	0.155	1.38	9.39
E	4.75	10.50	45.50	26.00	2.610	0.130	1.35	13.96
F	4.50	9.50	43.00	28.44	2.634	0.135	2.06	12.94
G	4.00	9.00	47.00	31.48	2.660	0.126	1.64	11.94
H	3.50	7.75	48.50	38.00	3.080	0.140	1.94	10.47
I	3.00	6.50	43.00	40.42	3.500	0.184	2.00	10.29
X ¹⁷	2.14	3.51	72.70					
Y ¹⁷	1.62	2.87	80.00					

^aCure rate is the slope of the ascending portion of the rheometric curve.

^bK is α(R_∞ - R₀) k_x/2, where α is conversion factor and k_x is specific rate constant.

E is the activation energy of the compound.

X is S/TMTD mix.

Y is S/ZDC mix.

Fig. 2. Plots of [(R_∞ - R_t)/(R_∞ - R₀)] vs cure time for sulfur cured NR gum stocks accelerated by CBS, CBS/TMTD and CBS/ZDC. For explanation of symbols (A to I) vide Table 1.

It includes the conversion factor of rheometer torque (*R*) to the amount of crosslinks and the probability of the formation of effective crosslinks by the reaction of these interme-

diates (*A*); and *k_x* is the specific rate constant of the second order crosslinking reaction, then⁸

$$\text{This gives } -dA/dt = k_x A^2 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{or, } 1/A - 1/A_0 = k_x (t - t_0) \quad (6)$$

where *t*₀ is the end of the induction period and *A*₀ is the initial concentration of *A* at time *t*₀. Since

$$2A_0 = \alpha (R_{\infty} - R_0) \text{ and } 2A = \alpha (R_{\infty} - R_t) \quad (7)$$

From eqns. (6) and (7)

$$(R_{\infty} - R_t)^{-1} - (R_{\infty} - R_0)^{-1} = (1/2) \alpha k_x (t - t_0)$$

or,

$$(R_{\infty} - R_0)/(R_{\infty} - R_t) = \{ \alpha (R_{\infty} - R_0) k_x (t - t_0)/2 \} + 1 \quad (8)$$

and by putting *K* = α (R_∞ - R₀) k_x/2,

$$(R_{\infty} - R_0)/(R_{\infty} - R_t) = K (t - t_0) + 1 \quad (9)$$

Here *K* is the apparent second order rate constant. The specific rate constant *k_x* can be calculated from eqn. (8), if constant α can be determined.

K values (Table 2) indicate that the mix system changes by changing the amount of the curative in NR compound. The variation in accelerator/sulfur ratio alters the *K* value.

This is clearly observed in the experimental compounds. In the CBS/S system, the K value increases with increase of accelerator/sulfur ratio. In the blend accelerator systems the results shows that the K value also depends on the nature of the accelerator. The S/CBS/ZDC system shows higher value than S/CBS/TMTD system. This is due to the higher chemical affinity of ZDC with NR.

Fig. 3 shows that the stocks cured by S/CBS/TMTD and S/CBS/ZDC satisfies eqn. (9). The plots show high slopes (stiff) for the blend systems. This indicates higher order reaction rate of the vulcanization reaction. For CBS system, lower slope straight-line plots may be due to the formation of some intermediates at high temperature. These react bimolecularly and satisfy eqn. (9). In all cases of the mixed accelerator systems, the second order rate becomes apparent only after a certain percentage of the total crosslinks (linearity of the Fig. 2). The tail end of the cure (curve portion of the plots in Fig. 2) takes the second order reaction in all the mixed accelerator stocks. Consequently, these accelerators in the mix are probably competing in the crosslinking reaction. The apparent reaction rate order is dependent on the reaction which controls rate at the various stages of curing processes.

Fig. 3. Second order crosslink formation of NR gum compounds cured by CBS and its mixes. For explanation of symbols (A to I) vide Table 1.

The formation of different polysulfides by the reaction with elemental sulfur in natural rubber are as follows⁹⁻¹¹:

where X is $RR'NC(=S)-$, thiocarbamyl in TMTD, ZDC and others.

where X is

The function of Zn-compound is to increase the rate of formation of the accelerator polysulfides from disulfides or sulfenamides. Zinc accelerator thiolates ($XSZnSX$) are sparingly soluble in rubber but are rendered soluble through coordination with zinc carboxylates¹¹ or with nitrogen bases¹². Accelerator polysulfides are the active sulfuring agent in the presence, as well as in the absence of zinc compounds. The initial step is usually thought to be a homolytic cleavage of the polysulfide to give persulfenyl radicals

These polysulfides can then react with the rubber molecule and form intermediates, which lead to crosslink formation at different rates. For the mixed accelerator systems, parallel crosslink reaction occurs. It is assumed that intermediates A and B react with rubber to form crosslinks :

where α' and α'' are constants with the same significance as α in previous case and R is the rheometric torque.

In CBS/TMTD and CBS/ZDC blend systems, one system is comparatively slower second order reaction and the other system is faster second order reaction (slope difference). But there is a common preliminary stage in which both the systems are mainly converted into polysulfides (XSS_aSX) and presumably gaining the hydrogen from the rubber¹³. So polysulfide is a common moiety in these combinations. This suggests that in combined accelerator systems, different ligands normally arise from the different accelerators may interact with each other with the common objectives of polysulfides formation. The kinetic results indicate that the state of crosslink formation is dependent on the structure of the accelerator used in the curing system.

In the three experimented types (S/CBS, S/CBS/TMTD and S/CBS/ZDC) of compound stocks, all the S/CBS systems are slow curing and give vulcanizates of low crosslink densities, excepting vulcanizate derived from D (Table 2)

than the other two types. The stocks of S/CBS/TMTD give the intermediate results. The fact that sulfenamides decompose to form ammonium mercaptides¹⁴. The actual reaction products are a mercaptan and an amine (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

This amine moiety, i.e. the basicity of the amine takes an important role in the TMTD or ZDC mixed stocks¹⁵.

Tetramethyl thiuram disulfide can dissociate basically in two ways¹⁶ (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Radical (I) can release sulfur for crosslinking. The radical (II) leads to the formation of zinc dithiocarbamates. The scission of the C-S bond (radical I) would be favoured by the amine moiety of ammonium mercaptide. Conversely, the homolytic cleavage (radical II) of the S-S bond by path (B) would be favourable by ϕ S-moiety (benzothiazyl sulfide).

Path-A gives higher crosslink density and path-B accelerates polysulfide formation. The lowering of the rate of cure and high scorch delay of S/CBS/TMTD or S/CBS/ZDC than S/TMTD or S/ZDC stocks¹⁷ may be due to the high stability of the benzothiazyl compound for its rigid and bulky structure. The crosslinking reactions of the stocks accelerated by these mixed system are nearer to a second order reaction. Therefore, in conclusion, the kinetics of crosslink formation of natural rubber stocks by curing system based on S/CBS and S/CBS/TMTD or S/CBS/ZDC varied with

phr (parts per hundred parts of rubber) of the accelerators and the structure of the accelerators.

Experimental

Natural rubber (RMA1 : Kerala Rubber Board, India) used had a Mooney viscosity, (1 + 4)(100°) of 72. The other compounding ingredients were as follows : zinc oxide (99% purity), stearic acid (Rubo Chem. Industries), CBS, TMTD, ZDC and IPPD (all I.C.I. Ltd., India), sulfur (98% purity, Standard Chemicals). The recipe of the experimented mixes is given in Table 1. All compounds were prepared on a laboratory size two-roll mixing mill (30 × 15 cm) at a friction ratio of 1 : 1.25 according to ASTM D3185-88.

The cure characteristics for various compound stocks were evaluated using a Monsanto rheometer (R100) with a micro-die and a 3° arc of oscillation at a temperature of 140° according to ASTM D2084-88. The vulcanization of test specimen was carried out in 46 cm × 46 cm platens using an electrically heated press maintained at 140° and 45 kg/cm² pressure. For each of the vulcanizates the value of M_c (the mean chain segment molecular weight) was evaluated by measuring equilibrium swelling volume in benzene¹⁸.

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